

**PARTICIPATION AND PROSPECTS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN
INTERNATIONAL RATINGS AND INDEXES****Usmanov Abdumomin Kholmomin ugli**

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizning ko'pgina ustuvor reytinglarda yuqorilab borayotgani, yurtimizda aholi turmush farovonligini oshirish, jamiyatimizda ochiqlik, oshkoralikni ta'minlash borasida qilinayotgan ezgu ishlarning mazmun-mohiyati, mamlakatimizning jahon hamjamiyatidagi nufuzini yanada yuksaltirishda xalqaro indekslarni ahamiyati hamda reyting agentliklarining metodologiyalarini o'rganish kabi masalalar to'g'risida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xalqaro hamkorlik, globallashuv, indeks, xalqaro reyting, tendentsiya, agentliklar.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение международных индексов в дальнейшем повышении престижа нашей страны в мировом сообществе, а также изучение методологий рейтинговых агентств.

Ключевые слова: международное сотрудничество, глобализация, индекс, международный рейтинг, тренд, агентства.

Abstract. In this article, the importance of international indexes in further increasing the prestige of our country in the world community, as well as studying the methodologies of rating agencies, are discussed in this article is discussed.

Keywords: international cooperation, globalization, index, international rating, trend, agencies.

Human development, processes of globalization in all spheres, quality and structural changes, while raising international cooperation and relations to a new level, impose the task of every independent country to look at these situations in a new way and take a step with them. This is determined, first of all, by the country's position on the world scale, its position in international rankings and indicators.

Creativity continue at a rapid pace in every aspect of life. Naturally, the result of such updates is reflected not only in the life of our people, but also in the indicators of prestigious international ratings and indexes. It should be said that international ratings and indexes reflect the development process of each country, and many important aspects such as the quality of public administration, the standard of living of the population, the protection of human rights, business activity and a favorable environment for foreign investors, sustainable economic growth and competitiveness. is good. These aspects are embodied in the essence of reforms in our country. All this acquires a deeper meaning as it serves to glorify human dignity, to ensure that people live contentedly and contentedly with life. The decree "On improving the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international rankings and indexes and introducing a new mechanism of systematic work with them in state bodies and organizations" adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan takes the work in this direction to a new stage in our country. was an important program in the development.

The republican council for working with international ratings and indices was established, and parliamentary control was established in the field. International rankings and indices are tools accepted by the world community as a key condition for economic development in assessing the

quality of the institutional environment in the world. They are used not only by experts, but also at the state level as a criterion for reforms and socio-economic policies.

In recent years, our country has been increasing in many priority ratings, which is an important result of the good work done in order to improve the living conditions of the population in our country, to ensure openness and transparency in our society. For example, recently the report of the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) on the "Competitive Industrial Productivity Index" was published. Our country was represented in it for the first time and took the 92nd place among 152 countries, the 5th place among the CIS member states, and the 2nd place among the countries of Central Asia.

It should be said that today the main goal of reforms in our society is directed towards the noble goal of pleasing our people. This goal is embodied in all our efforts, reforms, laws and decisions we make. The more the population is satisfied with the current policy, the higher our position in various ratings and indexes will be.

At the same time, there are still many tasks to be done in this direction. Based on the decree of the President, the purpose of controlling the effectiveness of state bodies at the highest, i.e. parliamentary level, is to increase the responsibility of heads of ministries and agencies in this regard. Therefore, the republican council for working with international ratings and indices was established. Taking into account the election of deputies and senators of the Oliy Majlis by the people, this mechanism means that people's control over the implementation of measures in the field is established. Now the heads of the ministries and agencies are reporting to the republican council on the work done to improve the indicators in the ratings and indexes for which they are responsible and on the performance of the assigned tasks.

In international rankings and indexes largely depends on the local implementation of the laws we adopt. That is why local governors were included in the council. This allows timely identification of problems related to the local implementation of legal requirements and their elimination.

Through this, mutual cooperation of the parliament, ministries and agencies and local governments in the work of this direction is ensured, cases of censorship are prevented, and all work is organized in a coordinated manner. Of course, this is one of the new processes that takes a lot of time and requires progressive knowledge. This is, without a doubt, consistent study of the international rating and index methodology assigned to the responsible state bodies, being able to apply it in practice while being able to interpret it correctly, establishing relations with the organization that provides the international rating and index. related to receiving. At the same time, our main task is to ensure the effective implementation of laws and other regulatory legal documents, in a word, the rule of law. In this regard, in our republic, we have begun to strictly establish parliamentary and public control, and we are achieving positive results.

In particular, negotiations were held with the responsible leaders of the organization in order to recognize Uzbekistan in the "Index of Restrictions on Regulation of Foreign Direct Investments" of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. In particular, agreements were reached with the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development on the development of the report "Investment Policy Review - Uzbekistan" and thereby expanding the possibilities of reflecting the country's position in the index.

Cornell University, the Ministry of Innovative Development is conducting negotiations on the issue of reflecting the place of our country in the "Global Innovation Index" of the International Intellectual Property Organization. Collaborative work is now underway to compile the necessary

statistical data required by this index. In addition, the statistical data required in some ratings and indexes are based on the statistical data base formed by the state agencies and organizations of our republic.

A total of 206 national indicators have been approved in the "Sustainable Development Goals" of the UN. The necessary information in this regard is constantly posted on a special site created by the State Statistics Committee. In addition, the necessary information for international ratings and indexes is regularly updated by government agencies.

For example, the "Open Data Portal" has been launched within the framework of the government portal. This portal coordinates the maintenance and updating of the open database of state bodies and organizations of the State Statistics Committee, as well as the timely display of relevant information.

In general, international rating and index management organizations rely on the results of surveys conducted among entrepreneurs and residents, information from non-governmental non-profit organizations, and conclusions of national and foreign experts. This, in turn, shows to what extent local residents and entrepreneurs are aware of reforms in the economic, political and social spheres and their results. Basically, our country ranks relatively low in the political-legal rating and indices. For example, it ranks 191st in the Freedom of Speech and Accountability Index, 184th in the Regulatory Quality Index, 183rd in the Corruption Control Index, 182nd in the Rule of Law Index, and 156th in the World Press Freedom Index. We are in line. In particular, necessary conditions have been created for freedom of speech and mass media to operate without restrictions and obstacles in our country. The Public Fund for the Support and Development of the National Mass Media was established in order to create equal conditions for mass media in the media market and to further develop them, as well as to support journalists and bloggers.

The Law "On Combating Corruption" was adopted in order to regulate relations in the field of combating corruption. The National Anti-Corruption Council was established in order to organize the development and implementation of state programs in this regard, to coordinate the activities of various bodies and organizations, and to form an uncompromising attitude towards corruption in the society. Anti-corruption agency was established, which implements state policy in the field of prevention and fight against corruption.

The rapid development of legislation related to changes in a number of areas has led to the emergence of many norms that conflict with the current legislation in some cases. That is why the concept of improving the activity of Norm creativity was developed in order to fundamentally revise the legislation, systematize it, improve the quality of the processes of development and adoption of normative legal documents, and improve the monitoring of their implementation.

However, despite all these efforts, indicators in the indices show that we still have shortcomings in this regard. Therefore, we have defined a number of important tasks. First of all, it will be necessary to develop a long-term strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan to fight against corruption. We also want to establish a procedure for mandatory assessment of corruption risks in state bodies and form a rating on prevention of corruption in the field of public administration. At the same time, we should also study the issue of our country becoming a member of the international organization of the Group of States Against Corruption (GREKO) and implementing the requirements of the relevant anti-corruption conventions of this organization into our national legislation.

It is necessary to further strengthen the organizational and legal basis for ensuring mass media, diversity of opinions and freedom of speech. In particular, we need to establish liability for offenses related to obstruction of the journalist's legitimate professional activity.

One of the reasons why the republic is at the bottom of the political-legal ratings and indexes is that these ratings and indexes are formed mainly on the basis of public opinion and the conclusion of international experts. In addition, taking into account the fact that the questionnaires of the index management organizations are conducted only in cooperation with independent civil society institutions (non-governmental non-profit organizations), factors such as the lack of such organizations on the republican scale and their limited capacity to carry out research may be the reason for this. At this point, we need to note that it would be appropriate if public councils consisting of representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations were formed in each state body, especially the ministry, department, and organization at the republic level, and close cooperation with them was established.

In Uzbekistan, some increases were observed in the components forming the overall rating. For example, the indices of "Human capital", "electronic participation" and "Telecommunications infrastructure" of this rating increased from 0.01 to 0.14 points. According to the "Electronic participation" index, our republic increased its index to 0.80 points, increased its position in the overall rating by 13 places, and took 46th place among countries with a very high level of development of the electronic participation index. entered the list. However, in 2018, according to this index, our country was in 59th place.

In addition, Uzbekistan was given the highest score for open data. Of course, some factors influenced the decrease of our place in the rating of "e-government development". first of all, it should be noted that from 2018 to April of this year, there was no single coordinating body for the development of the digital economy and the introduction of the "electronic government" system in our republic. As a result, a clearly defined plan of measures to increase the rating was not adopted and related work was not sufficiently organized. Currently, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development is responsible for this work.

Also, we cannot say that the national e-services portal and the websites of relevant ministries and agencies in the fields of education, labor, social services, health, finance and environment are fully responsive. These sites are evaluated on 148 aspects in the "electronic services" component of the rating. Mobile-friendly forms of the national online services portal and official websites have not been implemented sufficiently. Also, the low level of transaction services, the incomplete electronic payment of state duties, various fees and fines have a negative impact on our ranking.

There are also some shortcomings that we need to work on in the "Human capital" component of the rating. For example, distance education opportunities are not fully used, accurate information on the population with higher education is insufficient, affecting our position in the ranking.

In the "Telecommunications infrastructure" component, which determines the share of mobile subscribers and Internet users, the fact that the high-speed wired Internet network did not reach remote areas of the republic also affects our place in the rating. We have set priorities for correcting these shortcomings. We hope that the position of our country will be further improved in this direction in the next reports.

In conclusion, in any situation, based on the ancient values of our people, the feeling of always having good intentions and feeding with hope for tomorrow lives in our hearts. We are sure

that if all of us, the whole nation, work together as one soul, one body, we will come out with new conclusions, new ideas, and new strength, which will determine the future directions of our development, and we will continue the development path consistently.